

Germplasm improvement

Genetic resources

Mobile genetic elements useful for classifying and determining relationships between rice strains

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Morphological and physiological studies have played an important role in classifying species in the genus *Oryza*. Although detailed information on the classification of rice species has been accumulated with the development of molecular biological technology, relationships between *Oryza* species with AA genome have not been clarified.

We have identified 37 members of p-SINE1, a plant SINE (short interspersed elements) first found in rice (see figure), located at various loci. Most of these members are at the corresponding loci in *Oryza* species with the AA genome. However, several of them are present in a few *Oryza* species. Besides those described previously, a member of p-SINE1-r30 is only in *O. sativa*, p-SINE1-r29 is in all the AA genome *Oryza* species except for *O. longistaminata*, and p-SINE1-r25 is in all of the AA genome *Oryza* species except for *O. meridionalis* (see table).

Another member, p-SINE1-r38, contained an insertion that was 1536 bp long, with imperfect terminal inverted repeats of about 13 bp beginning with 5'-CACTA—3' (see figure). The insertion is

Distribution of p-SINE1^a

Species	p-SINE1-r30	p-SINE1-r29	p-SINE1-r25	p-SINE1-r38
<i>O. sativa</i> cv Nipponbare	+	+ ^b	±	+ ^c
cv IR36	+	+	±	+ ^c
<i>O. glaberrima</i> W025	—	+	+	+ ^c
<i>O. longistaminata</i> W1451 P1	—	—	+	—
<i>O. meridionalis</i> W1625	—	+	—	+
<i>O. glumaepatula</i> W1192	—	+	±	+ ^c

^ap-SINE1 members identified in *O. sativa*. The presence or absence of each p-SINE1 member at the respective locus was examined by PCR using a relevant pair of primers that hybridize to the regions flanking the p-SINE1 member. + and — indicate that the fragments with or without p-SINE1, respectively, are generated by PCR. ^bPCR fragments with p-SINE1 have a tandem duplication. ^cPCR fragments with p-SINE1 contain *Tnr3*. ± indicates that both fragments with and without p-SINE1 are generated by PCR.

Structures of p-SINE1 (a) and p-SINE1-r38 (b).

similar to that of the members of the En/Spm transposable element family such as En/Spm in maize, Tam1 in snapdragon, Tgm1 in soybean, Pis1 in pea, and Tpn1 in Japanese morning glory. This insertion sequence is thus named *Tnr3* (transposable element in rice #3). The *Tnr3* also carries long subterminal regions containing direct and inverted repeats of short DNA sequences of 15 bp, another characteristic of

the En/Spm family. *O. sativa*, *O. rufipogon*, *O. glaberrima*, and *O. glumaepatula* contain p-SINE1-r38 with *Tnr3*, but *O. meridionalis* contains only p-SINE1-r38 (see table). *O. longistaminata*, however, does not contain p-SINE1-r38.

The p-SINE1 members listed in the table might become useful DNA markers for classifying and determining relationships among *Oryza* species with AA genome. ■

Cytological analysis of a natural hybrid between *Oryza minuta* and *O. officinalis*

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Intergenic or interspecific hybrids are important for studying the evolutionary relationships between plant species, particularly those occurring spontaneously in nature. One *Oryza* population collected in 1990 from San Roque, Hilongos, Leyte, Philippines (P90-18; by D. A. Vaughan, L. Engle, N. Altoveros, E. Quintana, and T. Borromeo) was completely sterile, with nondehiscent anthers, nonstainable pollen grains, and no seed set. Morphologically,

this population resembled *O. minuta* J. S. Presl. ex C. B. Presl., a tetraploid *Oryza* species endemic to the Philippines that has 48 chromosomes containing two distantly related genomes (BBCC). This population was originally identified as "sterile *O. minuta*" and maintained in a nursery greenhouse for further observation.

Cytological observation of both root tip cells and pollen mother cells (PMCs) confirmed this population is a triploid